

Nyddfwch Compartment Draft Notes 2019

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Places and Placenames

The valley has had over a thousand years of settlement with successive generations naming and renaming things to reflect their activities and their daily lives.

These are the most common names used to describe places in use today. Where possible, the names of earlier farms and settlements are used to recognise the earlier settlements. Glyn Shilling is an old farm near the eastern boundary. Some names such as Nyddfchwch are from the earliest recorded history of the valley and may date from a time before the early medieval town of Swenes' (Swansea) was established in the 1100s.

The main river is now known as the Afon Llan probably in recognition of the many monastic and church watermills in the area. In medieval times it was known as the Lesser Lliw (the Greater Lliw is further west).

The placename of Nyddfchwch may indicate that the river has an earlier name of 'Nidd' which fell into disuse in the 1100s.

Tracks and Paths

Although there are many paths through the valley, some are far better than others.

The red lines are good quality surfaces that are generally easy to walk and are a good surface for pushchairs etc. You won't get muddy if you keep to these ones.

The green paths are generally poorer and may be muddy in bad weather. These ones are not so good for wheels, you will see a lot more nature on the green paths.

Over the years, walkers have created many other tracks through the woodland and along the river. Take care on these as they can be muddy with uneven surfaces and full of puddles in bad weather.

Take extra care around the river where the trip hazards from

0 100 200 300 400 500 m

1:9000

The most important path runs the length of the valley and is known as the Carriage Drive. This was built in the 1830s to allow horse buggies to enter the estate at Cadle and ride up through the gardens to the estate house which was near the office and car park.

Streams

The river we now call Afon Llan has a long history. It threads for nearly 3km inside the valley. Above the M4, the river can be traced back for over 12km. Below Cadle, the Llan flows for 4.5 km before it joins the Afan Lliw.

The Upper Lake was formed by building a dam in the 1830s. The lake and waterfall became a central point of the ornamental park developed by the nineteenth-century landowner. The lake is about 0.9ha in extent and is prone to silting up as the river transports massive amounts of silt.

Nant Gelly Evan and Nant Glyn Shilling are large streams that also have a long history.

Nant Gelly Evan was an important boundary and Nant Glyn Shilling supplied water for the mills at Cadle.

The Lower Lake was completed as part of further ornamental improvements in the early 1840s. A large earth dam allowed for flooding a large part of the flood plain. At its greatest extent in the 1800s, the lake may have been about 4.5ha in size.

Although a large body of water, the lake silted up very quickly and the margins became areas of marsh and swamp. The earth dam was not built to modern safety standards and was breached in the early 1960s allowing the river to run free once again.

In 2002 a smaller 'offline' lake of about 0.9ha area was built as part of an improvement scheme. The lake suffers badly from invasive non-native species and heavy pedestrian use.

Conservation Compartments

To make conservation management and planning easier we subdivide the valley into a series of zones or compartments. The word 'compartments' is something derived from forestry commission plans in the 1950s, nowadays modern plans may refer to zones which are basically the same thing.

We try to give compartments easily recognisable boundaries so that people know where they are in the woods. Compartments are temporary things and we will most likely change a number of these as we learn more about the urban nature of the valley.

In naming the compartments we've tried to reflect some of the past history of the valley, such as using old farm names or important characteristics of the land.

Nyddfwch

Description

The Nyddfwch compartment in the centre of the valley is the most historic area that we know of. The placename of Nyddfwch was well known in the 1100s and may belong to the era before the town of Swenes' (Swansea) was established.

A walk up to the top of Banc Nyddfwch has the treat of being the best viewpoint in the valley.

Generations of fire damage have transformed the vegetation into large stands of continuous bracken. Many of the surviving trees bear the scars of bracken fires. Climate change is now starting to transform Nyddfwch into new woodland with a lot of birch and oak regeneration.

As long as there are no substantial fires, the bracken cover is about to diminish under a mass of new woodland.

Nyddfwch has very clear boundaries and extends from Middle Lodge in the north to the *Nant Efail Wen* in the south, and the Carriage Drive to the east. It is likely to contain a significant amount of archaeology around the site of the ancient farmhouse in the centre of the compartment.

The ancient road connecting the farmhouse to the early medieval road is still prominent and needs protection. Generations of fire damage have resulted in areas of C1 bracken habitat. A recent reduction in arson attacks means that woodland regeneration is increasing. The southern field of bracken is likely to be heavily fragmented by natural regeneration in the next three years and will diminish rapidly.

A small number of large ancient and veteran trees remain. There are some substantial veteran sycamore hedges adjoining the farmhouse site which are an important part of the historic landscape. There are a

number of substantial hedgebanks in Nyddfwch, currently these are largely submerged in bracken but they could be reinstated if we adopt a hedgerow recreation target. There may be at least 400m of potential hedgerow habitat in Nyddfwch.

The remains of the old reservoir are a focus of mammal activity and retain some water and marshland in the winter.

Requirements

Nyddfwch is probably on the verge of a significant transformation from large areas of bracken to young woodland. This process is entirely natural and will accelerate in the coming years. It's necessary to make a strategic decision whether to accept the natural regeneration process or expend resources to intervene to amend the developing habitat.

Any interventions such as planting or strimming must be part of the wider valley conservation management plan as they will require regular commitment over several years. We require an agreement over what types of habitats are to be supported on Nyddfwch.

To bring Nyddfwch into Favourable Conservation Status (FCS), the following statements must be true:

- The area of the habitat(s) must be stable in the long term or increasing.
- Its quality (including ecological structure and function) must be maintained.
- Any typical species in the habitat must also be at FCS,
- The factors that affect the habitat, including its typical species, must be under control.

So, for example, Continuous bracken is declining and broadleaved and mixed woodland is increasing.

The archaeology on Nyddfwch is likely to be significant which imposes a constraint on digging or landscaping. Some of the trees planted on the Nyddfwch road site should be removed.

Nyddfwch is popular with adventurous walkers and trail runners. The main paths are popular and busy. These paths need to be maintained or kept clear subject to path standards across the rest of the Penllergare Trust area. There is no requirement to increase the length, quality, or number of access paths.

Creating refugia for reptiles on *Banc Nyddfwch* will increase opportunities for reptiles. This could be completed in conjunction with hedgerow restoration.

Creating refugia and ponds in the northern area will increase opportunities for reptiles and amphibians. The old reservoir could be easily reinstated with little cost.

The lower part of the reservoir stream could be used to create ponds.

The bulk of the woodland is young and it is worth considering a tree veteranisation project to accelerate veteran woodland creation. Some of the woodland in the north may be sufficiently secluded for a modest nest box pilot.

Conservation Status

Nyddfwch has only general protection and there is no active conservation.

Factors causing loss or decline

Fire remains the most serious risk with very high impact on the land-

Nyddfwch

Locations map 2019

Nyddfwch

Bracken plan 2019

Approximately 4.6 ha of continuous bracken in early 2019. This is likely to decline fast as woodland regeneration accelerates.

Although currently very good habitat for reptiles, bracken will only be held at 4 ha by fires or excessive strimming.

The southern portion at Nyddfwch bank does have large paths/firebreaks that could be maintained to provide woodland edge habitat in future years. Maintaining the Nyddfwch paths as 'woodland edge' would require irregular strimming clearance and provide over 600 metres of good quality semi-open mosaic habitat which would be good for reptiles.

Nyddfwch

Track plan 2019

Coordinates
262533,198350

These are the paths that need to be maintained in the compartment. There are approximately 1.88 km of paths here.

Nyddfwch

Woodland plan 2019

Approximately 4.6 ha of continuous bracken in early 2019. This is likely to increase fast as woodland regeneration accelerates.

The paths through the woodland may have to be trimmed to wider margins for safety. They could also, if managed carefully, contribute to a larger graded-woodland edge habitat target. If so, the woodland paths could contribute over 600m of woodland edge habitat.

This woodland will essentially be a variation of a Lowland Mixed Deciduous woodland habitat. It will be varied because of local conditions allowing for more Ash and Birch than normally present. It will also have a significant of Rhododendron.

There is no need to add to this woodland by additional planting

scape. Basically, any large fire resets the regeneration to zero and ensured the southern land is held in a low-diversity bracken habitat.

Some paths are exposed to erosion because of visitor numbers.

The western area is drained by a series of drains built in the nineteenth century and repaired in recent years. The land is drier than it could be.

Rhododendrons are spreading in the northern area and increasingly in the south.

Desired outcome

To bring Nyddfych into Favourable Conservation Status.

Action

Accept that FCS is the target end state for this compartment.

Agree which Habitat Action Plans will be adopted for this compartment.

Agree which Species Action Plans will be adopted for this compartment.

Agree path maintenance activities for rest of financial year.

Ensure the current paths/firebreaks on Banc Nyddfych are assessed for further maintenance.

Agree volunteer plan for rest of financial year.

Prepare draft costing of time and resources allocated to maintenance and developing FCS of Nyddfych for rest of financial year.

Action to date

The bracken areas have been strimmed in the past and firebreaks were cut in 2017. These areas have been used as paths and the area has an established set of informal paths.

In 2014, a stand of trees were planted across the original approach road to the Nyddfych farmhouse site, obscuring the wider view and interpretation of the site.

Action and targets

Related Action plans

Species Action Plan: Common Lizard

Species Action Plan: Common Toad

Species Action Plan: Slow worm

Habitat action Plan: Deadwood

Habitat Action Plan: Ponds

Habitat Action Plan: Lowland mixed deciduous woodland

Key partners

References

Habitat Action Plan:

Lowland mixed deciduous woodland

Description

Lowland mixed deciduous woodland includes woodland growing on the full range of soil conditions, from very acidic to base-rich, and takes in most semi-natural woodland in southern and eastern England, and in parts of lowland Wales and Scotland.

It occurs within enclosed landscapes, usually on sites with well-defined boundaries, at low altitudes, although altitude is not a defining feature. Many sites are ancient woods and they include classic examples of ancient woodland and may have existed in some form since the 1600s or earlier. They are often rich in historic features such as old banks and ditches, the remains of buildings that were once part of local woodland industries, and ancient pollards and coppice stools.

The woods tend to be small, less than 20 hectares. Often there is evidence of past coppicing, particularly on moderately acid to base-rich soils; on very acid sands former wood-pastures of oak and birch may represent the type. There is wide variety in the species composition of the canopy layer and the ground flora, and this is reflected in the range of associated National Vegetation classification (NVC) and Stand Types. *Quercus robur* is the commoner oak (although *Quercus petraea* may be abundant locally, particularly in Wales) and may occur with all combinations of other locally native tree species. *Quercus robur* may have been extensively planted in the 1800s on estates and plantations, it may not have originated in local plantations as there was a ten-

dency to introduce oaks from the continent as they were considered superior to local strains. Oak on the Penllergare Estate in Swansea may have been imported from anywhere in Europe. It has hybridised with the local trees. Some ancient oaks in the Llan Valley pre-date the period of greatest imports and may be best suited for seed collection. Woodland flowers such as bluebell, early purple orchid and wood anemone all flourish in this habitat. In fact, the UK's bluebells make up almost 50% of the world's total population. Ancient Woodland Indicator plants (such as herb-Paris) can often be found. Open spaces can be good for wildflowers and a rich environment for insects (bees, wasps, hoverflies and butterflies). Lowland mixed deciduous woodland is important for wide range of birds including nightingales, spotted flycatchers, woodpeckers, tree creepers and nut-hatches.

In terms of the National Vegetation Classification (NVC) the bulk of this type falls into W8, W10 (and lesser amounts of W16. Locally, it may form a mosaic with other types, including patches of beech woodland, small wet areas, and types more commonly found in western Britain. Rides and edges may grade into grassland and scrub types. For more information on how the NVC is useful see Rodwell and Patterson (1994) *Bulletin* 112.

Requirements

The habitat should be at Favourable Conservation Status (FCS):

For a **habitat** feature to be at FCS, all the following must be true:

- The area of the habitat must be stable in the long term or increasing.
- Its quality (including ecological structure and function) must be maintained.
- Any typical species must also be at FCS. Typical species for the area may have to be determined/agreed by survey and later monitoring.
- The factors that affect the habitat, including its typical species, must be under control.

Distribution

National
Regional?
Site

Current Status

Legal Status

Conservation Status

Under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016, lowland deciduous woodland is a habitat of principal importance for the purpose of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

It now only covers about 1-2% of its original range. It has declined in area by clearance, overgrazing and replanting with non-native species, by about 30-40% over the last 50 years.

Desired Outcomes

This is one of the most diverse woodland types with a great variety of composition and structure among the trees and shrubs of semi-natural stands. Design options are numerous, and additional variety can be encouraged around open areas and along margins where light-demanding shrubs like dogwood, purging buckthorn and privet can be concentrated. The colourful herbaceous flora characteristic of open margins, and especially well seen after coppicing, establishes only slowly, but damper rides and clearings can develop diverse tall-herb vegetation fairly quickly provided taller grasses can be held in check by strimming.

Action

Major Recommended trees for planting

- Ash
- Pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*)
- Sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*)
- Wych elm (to the north-west of the zone)
- Field maple
- Silver birch
- (An occasional group of conifers amongst the planting can provide a valuable extra niche for birds).

However, Penllergare will not need to plant oak or birch.

Minor recommended trees for planting

- Downy birch
- Silver birch
- Holly
- Crab apple
- Rowan
- Aspen
- Grey willow

- Gean (locally)
- Common whitebeam (locally)
- Hornbeam (to the south and east)
- Wych elm (to the north-west)

Recommended shrubs for planting

Major recommended shrubs

- Hazel
- Hawthorn

Minor recommended shrubs

- Blackthorn
- Elder
- Guelder rose
- Goat willow
- Wild privet
- Dogwood (England and Wales only)
- Spindle (England and Wales only)
- Wayfaring tree (England and Wales only)
- Purging buckthorn (England and Wales only)
- Alder buckthorn (locally)
- Common gorse/whin (in more open places)
- Broom (in more open places)

Tree Veteranisation

This is creating intentional damage on younger trees to speed up the process of habitat creation.

- Cutting a nestbox into living oak.
- Ring-bark a branch.
- Create woodpecker holes.
- Break or rip branches away.

Key Partners

Related Action Plans

Other BAPs

References

Broadmeadow, MSJ & Ray, D (2005) Climate Change and British Woodland. Research Note. Forestry

Commission. Edinburgh.

JNCC, 2008, UK Biodiversity Action Plan Priority Habitat Descriptions, <http://jncc.defra.gov.uk/page-5706> accessed February 2018.

Peterken, G.F. (1981) *Woodland conservation and management*. London: Chapman & Hall.

Rackham, O. (1980) *Ancient woodland*. London: Arnold.

Rodwell, John S; Patterson, Gordon S. 1994. Creating New Native Woodlands Bulletin 112. HMSO, London.

UK National Ecosystem Assessment – Chapter 8 Woodland

Quine, C., Cahalan, C., Hester, A., Humphrey, J., Kirby, K., Moffat, A. and Valatin, G. (2011). Woodlands, chapter 8 of UK National Ecosystem Assessment, UNEP-WCMC/Defra, London.

Habitat Action Plan: Deadwood

Description

Deadwood is an important part of any woodland. In fact, it is so important that it should really have its own habitat action plan to ensure it is given the proper consideration in a conservation project. 20% of woodland species depend on dead or dying wood for all or part of their lifecycle. There is a direct relationship between the amount of dead wood in a woodland and its biodiversity. Usually we use the term 'deadwood' to include all types of dead or dying trees of 10 cm or more in diameter. This can range from whole or wind-snapped standing trees, fallen wood and stumps, through to decaying wood habitats on living trees. For centuries across all of Europe, deadwood was a bad thing. Sick, dying, or dead trees were removed constantly in the fear of spreading disease, safety, fire risks and general tidiness. The past decade has seen a realisation that this view is wrong and that the removal of deadwood has had negative effects on the normal functioning of a woodland. Deadwood can come in many forms, but we can see five main types in a normal woodland:

Veteran Trees. Dead wood can be an important part of a healthy tree.

Standing dead trees. Often called 'snags', these can be trees damaged or destroyed by disease or weather conditions. They will eventually fall but they provide essential habitat for insects and birds.

Windthrown trees. Every winter in every woodland will

provide trees that have been uprooted by the wind. Fallen trunks die quickly and may provide food and ground shelter for decades.

Fallen Deadwood. Trees can shed branches which quickly develop their own local plant and animal communities on the woodland floor.

Stumps. The remains of trees can provide seed bed for new tree seedlings and excellent habitat for fungi, bryophytes, and invertebrates.

Requirements

Woodland biodiversity can only recover successfully with plentiful supplies of deadwood in all its forms. Generation of deadwood is often a question of allowing natural processes to run. Allowing aging and dead trees to remain in a woodland is the easiest way. In London's Olympic Park rotting and dead wood was imported into the new wildlife areas to kick-start the process. Reducing clearance of wood or defining zones where less clearance will take place can help the process.

It is also important to ensure good linkage and connectivity between deadwood habitats. This can be a problem in some areas of public access where aesthetics and health and safety forces clearance of deadwood. Best approach is to take a landscape view of the site and plan areas of 'high value' deadwood habitat that link to each other in areas of lower value open woodland for public access.

Distribution

Site

Not yet surveyed.

Current Status

Legal Status

There is no legal status for deadwood although the UK Woodland Assurance Standard (UKWAS) does have a requirement for about 20 m³/ha, excluding tree stumps, should be provided across the whole Woodland Management Unit and the greatest volumes concentrated in areas of higher ecological value.

Conservation Status

Deadwood is a vital part of any biodiversity action plan

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

Removal. Deadwood makes great firewood and is often removed from woodlands to be used as fuel. Deadwood is also removed from parks and public woodlands

Uniform Age and Species Structure across many woodlands means that older trees are rare, or deadwood has not yet been accumulated.

Loss of traditional woodland management: Woodlands are one of the few natural habitats in Britain that have historically benefited from human activity. Traditionally our woodlands were managed to produce a variety of fuel and building

materials, food, and hunting opportunities. Different traditional practices such as coppicing and pollarding meant that areas of woodland where opened up, allowing more light to the woodland floor and therefore encouraging more ground flora. Regular and varied harvesting also meant that many deadwood habitats were created.

Fertilisers and Pesticides: Many large farms and plantations spray pesticides on their crops. These pesticides can very easily be absorbed by deadwood which then kills any invertebrates living within it, or animals that then eat the invertebrates.

Desired Outcomes

To be able to meet or exceed the UKWAS standard for deadwood of 20 cubic metres per hectare.

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

Undertake a survey and assessment of the current deadwood habitat using a standard method (e.g. Forestry Commission). Assessed land can be classified as Low, Medium, and High value and actions such as connectivity and deadwood management can be evidence-based. By December 2019.

We can give nature a helping hand by artificially injuring or felling trees. This can be of great benefit where there is currently a lack of habitat or there is a need to ensure continuity of habitat after a period of change or redevelopment.

Make deadwood piles near native trees and shrubs and waterways (if possible).

Look for damper areas to build log piles in and put some in sunny open conditions and some in shady areas.

When funds allow, some trees can be 'veteranised' to simulate the natural damage of years of life by:

- Cutting nest boxes into tree trunks;
- Ring-barking selected branches;
- Create 'woodpecker' holes;
- Break or rip branches to create tears for the weather and fungal attack.

All these techniques can be used around key veteran trees to create a wider 'mature' habit in years rather than decades.

Key Partners

Related Action Plans

Other BAPs

References

Forest Enterprise, (2002), *Life in the Deadwood*, Edinburgh.

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Thompson, R.N., Humphrey, J.W., harmer, J.W., and Ferris, R., (2003), *Restoration of native woodland on ancient woodland sites*. Forestry Commission Practice guide, Edinburgh.

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Habitat Action Plan: Ponds

Description

Ponds can be especially important in woodlands because they provide ideal conditions for dragonflies, amphibians and bats. Many woodland plants will also grow well in very wet marsh or pond conditions. Many Welsh woodlands have few ponds, probably because any that existed have long been drained or removed after generations of woodland management in an era when the true value of ponds was not recognised.

Requirements

The pond habitats should be at Favourable Conservation Status (FCS):

For a **habitat** feature to be at FCS, all the following must be true:

- The area of the habitat must be stable in the long term or increasing.
- Its quality (including ecological structure and function) must be maintained.
- Any typical species must also be at FCS. Typical species for the area may have to be determined/agreed by survey and later monitoring.
- The factors that affect the habitat, including its typical species, must be under control.

We need to build a range of sizes. Ponds can be as small as the size of a bath or as large as a hectare in size. Large ponds are rare. The northern edge of the enterprise

zone in Swansea has an excellent range of ponds which are splendid examples of the quality ponds can bring to any landscape.

One pond on its own is good...but a group of ponds of different shapes and sizes across an area is much better.

Distribution

National

There may be about 400,000 ponds in the UK. Although this seems a substantial number it is a small fraction of what we really should have.

Site

Current Status

Legal Status

Many large ponds get protection as they are part of SSSIs. Smaller ponds tend not to have statutory protection. Ponds are often chosen as local (non-statutory) wildlife sites by county councils which gives them some protection in local development plans.

Conservation Status

Under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016, ponds are a habitat of principal importance for the purpose of supporting and enhancing biodiversity.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

In the UK in recent decades, many areas of ponds and standing water

have been lost or degraded. We may have lost 75% of our ponds in the past 100 years. The factors that threaten ponds are:

- Water pollution, especially nutrient enrichment.
- Adjacent land-use changes leading to loss of waterside vegetation and siltation and habitat fragmentation.
- Loss of the complementary terrestrial habitat. Ponds in isolation (e.g. without surrounding vegetation) are rarely successful.
- Water abstraction leading to drying out of ponds.
- Infilling, tipping, draining and built environment.
- Neglect and lack of proper management (leading to siltation and succession).
- Introduction and manipulation of fish stocks for angling.
- Introductions of non-native plants and animals.
- Recreational disturbance.

Desired Outcomes

Several ponds of varied sizes and depths at Favourable Conservation Status (FCS).

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

We need to build a range of sizes.

Ponds can be as small as the size of a bath or as large as our two lakes. However, our two lakes are not ponds because they are connected to the river and have different plants and animals (and deposition and erosion) because of river flow

Even tiny pools will support wildlife. They are quick and easy to construct so volunteers can quickly get to make something important that will be significant for our wildlife. Ponds that are only 5 cm deep work well. They only ever need to be about 40cm deep at their deepest point.

Ponds must be larger to attract wetland bird species. Sometimes they need to be very large. It is hard to predict how they will be used, for example, the shallow flooded building plots on the nearby Felindre building development sites attract large numbers of birds and the two lakes in the adjacent Penllergare/Llan valley attract very few.

What is certain is that we will get many more species with large numbers of small ponds instead of small numbers of big ponds.

Many woodlands don't have the capacity or suitable locations for large ponds. But the opportunities for small ponds are endless!

The best water sources are:

Groundwater. This can be under the surface or where it comes up to the surface (i.e. springs). We have lots of water sources along both sides of the valley.

Rain and surface water which drains off the land from surrounding woodland.

We do not use any water from the river, large streams, runoff from roads and tracks. These will all bring pollution or silt into the pond.

Ponds can be close together but not connected. Different ponds will quickly assume distinctive characteristics of drainage, water levels, plant assemblages and invertebrate communities. This is the biodiversity we want to achieve.

Where do we place ponds?

Ponds work best where there is plenty of water and good light conditions. They won't do well under dark tree canopies, but they will thrive under dappled shade. We need to place them in areas free of dog interference as dogs will disturb the mud and make the water cloudy. We also need to discourage people walking through the areas as foot traffic destroys the conditions of stability that we want to set up.

Areas that are already damp or have springs coming to the surface are ideal. In damp areas the water table is close to the surface, so it is far less effort to dig out pond basins. We can create ponds in drier areas, but we must dig deeper to reach the right layers in the ground where water accumulates.

We can place ponds in open glades, rides, and woodland edges. Sunny sheltered areas work best of all. A perfect site would be along the northern side of glade or ride that runs east to west, which ensures lots of sunny exposure. This is perfect for a series of small ponds which supply more shelter than bigger areas of water.

One pond on its own is good...but a group of ponds of different shapes and sizes across an area is much better. A mix of ponds is good for habitat diversity. We can add to the quality of a pond by sensitive planting of woodland plants around the margins. We won't need to plant anything in the pond itself...nature will do that for us. We can use the guidance in the biodiversity handbook on woodland edges and patch sizes to help design edges.

We only create good ponds in areas where they would naturally form. This is because we avoid using artificial pond liners. The best thing to do is rely on the underlying geology. We need to remove the leaf litter and underlying soil and dig down to the clay subsoil or at least to where we see increasing dampness occurring. We don't need to fill the pond with water. The weather will do that job for us!

Once you have the tools you need decide on the size of the teams. Two or three people can create a perfectly sized pond in a few hours. A decent size for a small pond is about the size of a bath, a bigger pond can be about the size of a car.

Mark out the size of the basin you want

to create use sticks to agree a size to work to. It can be quite easy to get confused over the size you are going for and end up digging out far more than you originally planned!

Rake off the upper leaf layer to expose the soil and start to loosen the earth. Use a spade to cut around the outline and use the mattock to break up the soil for excavation.

When you are digging out the soil...don't overload the spade as you will get tired very quickly get into a rhythm of moving lots of small spades of soil rather than big loads.

The excavated soil is not to be used for any of the pond work as it is too rich in nutrients and will contaminate the pond. Make sure you can remove it completely from the pond area...at least ten metres away is good.

You need to dig down to the subsoil or the clay layer...you will see a colour change as the clay is often a much lighter colour than the soil.

The sides of the pond must be shallow...very shallow so that there is a very gradual gradient into the middle of the pond. The pond only needs to be 40cm deep at its deepest point.

You can use the rake to create a nice shallow basin-shaped profile at the end of the dig.

We leave the pond to fill up naturally from rainwater or a groundwater source. We don't add water, plants, or animals from anywhere. We let the pond develop naturally. This is the way we ensure that the pond develops the best ecology that fits the local circumstances.

We must be patient. It may take a year for the pond to develop its own personality of plants and animals. Some will naturally silt up and become marshy areas and others will develop habitat for amphibians...we let the pond decide what to do!

The target is always to look to develop a natural collection of plants in the ponds. It is essential that no plants are artificially introduced from other sites. Plants will arrive in their own way and in their own time. Mobile species arrive quickly, and rarer species will take longer. There is always the risk that invasive non-natives will also arrive quickly. Early

arrivals are often stoneworts and bryophytes. The valley has many damp locations where these plants already flourish.

We record the location of the pond on our GPS map and we go back and look at it in a year's time.

Key Partners

Related Action Plans

Common frog

Common toad

Smooth newt

Other BAPs

References

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Species Action Plan: Common lizard

Description

The common lizard *Zootoca (lacerta) vivipara* ranges in colour from yellow-brown to olive-green with patterns of darker spots, flecks, or stripes. Males and females are distinguished from each other by their belly, males have an orange belly with black spots while females have a plain yellowish belly. An adult common lizard can grow to between 10 cm and 18 cm in length. Common lizards are active during the day, often basking in the morning and late afternoon sun, and hunting for food when their body temperature is high enough. As night falls, they seek shelter in the ground or beneath logs and stones. Common lizards hibernate from October or November to March.

Habitat

Common lizard lives in open and sunny habitats, such as rough grassland, woodland edge, road or rail embankments, marshes, moors, heathland, hedgerows, and open mosaic habitats.

Diet

Feeds on invertebrates, insects, spiders, and earthworms.

Biology and Reproduction

Males become sexually mature after two years, and females a year later. Courtship and mating follows hibernation, usually about May. The common lizard is a viviparous reptile meaning the female keeps the fertilised eggs inside her body until

they are ready to hatch.

National Distribution

Common lizard is native to Britain and can be found throughout the mainland.

Regional Distribution

Common throughout Wales.

Site Distribution

Legal Status

Under the Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981 the common lizard is protected from killing or sale. It is also listed in Appendix II of the Bern Convention (1982) which requires member states to ensure strict protection.

Conservation Status

In Wales common lizards are considered of principal importance for the purpose of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity, and they are a listed species under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016. Sadly, they don't currently have a Species Champion in UK Parliament or Welsh Assembly.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

Despite being widely distributed in UK, the population of common lizard has fallen in recent years. The main causes for this are thought to be habitat loss, fragmentation, and degradation due to changes in land use, scrub encroachment on grass-

land and uncontrolled fires.

Desired Outcome

To establish or enhance suitable habitat on the project site to make the area a suitable receptor site for a population of common lizard by 2020. A longer-term aim would be to establish a viable breeding population.

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

To establish and monitor several quiet, sunny, south-facing locations, on slopes at woodland edge locations or where species-rich grassland occurs.

Initial survey using a standard protocol.

Build more hibernacula in suitable areas based on the standard DfT designs and using natural material from the site. Build 10 hibernacula by 2020.

Install a regular monitoring programme to assess population development.

Related BAPs

Ponds

Trees and scrub

Common toad

Common lizard

Other Relevant BAPs

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Species Action Plan: Common toad

Description

The common toad (*Bufo bufo*) ranges from about 8 cm to 20 cm. The females are larger than the males. This species has a broad, squat body and a rounded snout. The toes are short, and the hind feet are webbed. Eyes are orange with black horizontal pupils. The skin is covered in raised warts, particularly on the back and sides. The colour of the skin varies according to the time of year, age, and area in which they live. Colouration can be dark brown, grey, olive, terracotta, or sandy with a grey-white underside. Toads are sometimes covered in darker markings on their backs. There are two prominent glands behind the eyes which produce an unpleasant and irritating secretion. The forelimbs of the male are thicker and the fingers shorter than those of the female. The male also has dark coloured nuptial pads on the inner three fingers of the forelimbs.

Habitat

Common toads inhabit deciduous woodland, scrub, gardens, parks, and fields. In the breeding season they live in ponds, lakes, and ditches. During the day, common toads tend to take refuge in holes in the ground or other damp areas such as leaf piles or compost heaps. They will use similar areas for hibernation during the winter months. At night they emerge to hunt for food in rough grass, woodland, scrub, or other suitable habitats. Toads only inhabit water during the spring breeding

season, when they will return to their ancestral ponds to lay their eggs, often making hazardous journeys across roads to reach these sites. Their tadpoles have generally become toadlets and leave the pond by the end of July.

Diet

Toads are opportunistic feeders eating a variety of invertebrates and anything they can swallow...slugs, snails, insects, etc. Usually they sit and wait predators, catching prey with their long tongues, however they will roam for food if needed. Larger toads occasionally eat slow worms, small grass snakes and mice, all of which are swallowed live.

Biology and Reproduction

The common toad reaches sexual maturity at the age of four. Toads emerge from hibernation in late February and head towards breeding ponds (they may return year after year to established ponds). The female common toad lays long strings of eggs, which are fertilised by the male which holds onto the female for several days/ Anything between 600 and 4000 eggs are laid. The adults leave the water once spawning is over. Tadpoles hatch within ten days. Despite being distasteful to most predators the majority will not reach adulthood. Metamorphosis of tadpole to toadlet can take up to twelve weeks depending on the availability of food and

water temperature. Toadlets usually leave the water during May. Toads spend most of their lives in terrestrial habitats. They are largely nocturnal and most active following rain.

National Distribution

Common toad is widespread in the UK. It occurs from the coast to upland areas...wherever there are suitable bodies of water for breeding and adequate vegetation for cover and food.

Regional Distribution

Toads are common throughout the area although records are poor.

Site Distribution

None have yet been recorded on the site.

Legal Status

The UK Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981 (as amended) prohibits the sale of common toads. A licence is needed for collection during the breeding season.

Conservation Status

In Wales common toads are considered of principal importance

for the purpose of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity, and they are a listed species under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016.

Common toads also have a 'Species Champion' within the Welsh National Assembly. In January 2018 the Common Toad Species Champion for Wales is Jeremy Miles AM for Neath.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

Destruction of breeding ponds is the prime cause of decline. Development within a toad's home range can mean isolation from the breeding pond. Common toads are killed crossing roads on their way to and from breeding ponds. Toads are particularly sensitive to pollution which can result in increases susceptibility to disease and parasite infestation. *Ranavirus* also causes toad death. Toads can easily become trapped in road drainage systems and gully pots.

Desired Outcome

To establish a breeding population of common toad within the project area by 2020 by creating four amphibian ponds.

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

Possible survey for presence

For example, only: Two new amphibian ponds each at least 40m² in area to be created adjacent to complementary terrestrial habitats by 2020. Two more ponds of the same

size created in the wider project area. Once ponds are vegetated, they many receive spawn from suitable donor sites.

Monitor presence of toads in the vicinity of the two initial ponds.

Related BAPs

Ponds

Trees and scrub

Common frog

Common lizard

Other Relevant BAPs

Brecon Beacons Local Biodiversity Action Plan?

References

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Species Action Plan: Slow worm

Description

The slow worm *Anguis fragilis* is a legless lizard up to 50 cm in length. Adults have cylindrical bodies with a smooth shiny grey or copper appearance. The female is usually black on the sides and sometimes with a dark stripe along the middle of its back.

Habitat

Slow worms are found in a wide range of open and partially shaded habitats including rough grassland and woodland edge. Slow worms seek refuge under wood, stones or debris and spend most of their lives underground or deep under vegetation.

Diet

Slow worms feed largely on slugs and other invertebrates which they hunt at dusk or after rainfall.

Biology and Reproduction

Slow worms emerge from hibernation in about March with mating occurring in May and June. Females typically give birth to about eight young around the end of August. Males become sexually mature at three or four years of age and females at four or five years.

National Distribution

Slow worms are widespread in Britain but particularly abundant in the south-west.

Regional Distribution

Common throughout the area.

Site Distribution

Not recorded on the site.

Legal Status

Under the Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981 the common lizard is protected from killing or sale.

Conservation Status

In Wales slow worms are considered of principal importance for the purpose of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity, and they are a listed species under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016. Sadly, they don't currently have a Species Champion in UK Parliament or Welsh Assembly.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

Populations are known to have suffered declines in recent years due to habitat loss following changes in land use and human

activities. Slow worms cannot travel far so they are vulnerable to isolation and fragmentation of habitat. Other factors contributing to decline are 'tidy' landscapes, persecution, and intensive farming.

Desired Outcome

To create an interconnected complex of lightly managed grassland and woodland edge habitats suitable for slow worms. Make the site suitable as a receptor site for animals rescued from development sites in the region.

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

Initial survey for presence of slow worms using a standard protocol.

Build additional hibernacula in suitable areas based on the standard DfT designs and using natural material from the site. Build 10 hibernacula by 2020.

Install a regular monitoring programme to assess population development.

Related BAPs

Common toad

Common lizard

Other Relevant

BAPs

Brecon Beacons Local Biodiversity Action Plan?

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Welsh Government, Environment

Species Action Plan: Birds

Description

Catering for birds is a challenge, the closer to an urban area we are, the greater the challenge is. We know a massive amount about the ecology of woodland birds and their preferences. We know that the number of bird species increases with the size of the wood. The fragmented woodland of 1980s Penllergare is now transforming into a larger block of connected woodland, so we should see an increase in diversity and numbers since the baseline survey in 2002.

Habitat

The ideal layout for maximising bird life is to have a mixture of large and small woods and shrub-by areas...which is what we now have.

Young woodland is attractive to doves, tree pipits, and various warblers.

Denser canopy attracts willow/garden warblers.

Mature woodland attracts marsh tits, nuthatches, tree creepers, willow tits, and woodpeckers.

We can create better rides and paths for birdlife by ensuring that any suitable ride is 1.5 times as wide as the height of the surrounding trees.

In some of our more mature woodland, rides may need to be 30 to 45 m wide. We can margin these rides with coppice or shrubs.

Marginal shrub belts need to be at

least 5 m wide, and in good areas 10-20 m.

Birds that breed in woodland will feed in the rides and hawks will hunt along them.

Alternatively, we could cut glades in quieter areas. These need to be at least 2500 square metres to be useful.

The planting of substantial belts of native shrubs or leaving an area to regenerate naturally will be an asset in attracting birds and insects.

Conifers attract coal tit and goldcrest, so we must keep conifers in the woodland mix in the valley.

Reconstituted hedgerows have proved to be particularly attractive to birds.

Diet

Insectivorous birds find more to eat on oak, birch, willow and sycamore. However they may prefer to roost in sweet chestnut, holly, larch and yew.

Nest Boxes

Young woodland suffers from a lack of opportunity for natural hole nesters. Most of the woodland is still too young to provide veteran trees. We could introduce a tree veteranisation programme to accelerate veteran tree formation. For further details see the habitat action plan for deciduous woodland.

Research in the mid 1990s confirmed that schemes that placed

nestboxes in newly restored areas as an attempt to increase the bird population failed because of food supply. Putting nest boxes in areas where there is insufficient food supply will run the risk of increased chick mortality. Any house sparrow action plan would involve installing nest boxes.

In Penllergare, placing nest boxes runs the risk of visitors vandalising or disturbing the birds. Many boxes put up in the past have been vandalised or destroyed.

Any nest box project needs to be carefully implemented in selected areas and monitored heavily.

Site Distribution

The 2002 Baseline Survey gives breeding territory and presence information for the species shown in the graph opposite.

Legal Status

Generally, birds enjoy more legal protection than any other kinds of animal. There are 51 birds listed under Section 7 of the Environment (Wales) Act 2016 for the purpose of maintaining and enhancing biodiversity in relation to Wales.

Conservation Status

In 2002, there were records of 10 Section 7 species residing in the valley:

- Bullfinch

- Cuckoo
- Dunnoek
- House Sparrow
- Kestrel
- Lesser Redpoll
- Marsh Tit
- Starling
- Song Thrush
- Tree Pipit

However, any birds in the valley should be afforded equal status and protection regardless of species.

Factors Causing Loss or Decline

Desired Outcome

Action

Action to Date

None.

Action and Targets

Related BAPs

Deciduous woodland

Other Relevant BAPs

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